

STUDY ON GERMINATION OF RAJMA (PHASEOLUS VULGARIS.L) IN AMENDED SOIL

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to investigate the effects of applying Plain Soil, Plain soil and vermicompost, Plain soil and Neem cake, Plain soil and inorganic fertilizers on germination of Rajma. Significant differences in germination percentage were observed between amended soil and Control (plain Soil).

The germination percentage was found maximum in plain soil followed by amended soil with urea followed by amended soil with vermicompost on 3rd day of seeding. On 4th day of seeding it was 100% in plain soil, 60% in vermicompost amended soil 80% in urea amended soil and 50% in neem amended soil. The conductivity and the protein content of the root stem and leaf has also been estimated.

Keywords: Germination percentage, vermicompost, plain soil

Introduction

French bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is one of the most important leguminous vegetables in India. It is also known as common bean or kidney bean. French bean is grown extensively because of its short duration and for nutritive values. It is a good source of protein, calcium, phosphorus, iron, carotene, thiamine, riboflavin and vitamin C. In India, it is grown for tender vegetables, shelled green beans and dry beans (Rajmah). One of the factors of low productivity of french bean is due to inadequate fertilization. Indiscriminate use of chemical fertilizers reduce nutritive value, whereas integration of organic and bio-fertilizers improve the soil health and plant nutrient availability resulting in higher crop yields besides being environmentally safe. The long term use of inorganic fertilizer without organic supplements damage the soil physical, chemical and biological properties and causes environmental pollution. Organic manures act not only as a source of nutrients and organic matter, but also increase size, biodiversity and activity of the microbial population in soil, influence structure, nutrients turnover and many other related physical, chemical, and biological parameters of the soil

The present investigation is to study the germination percentage of Rajma in different soil i.e. Plain soil and amended Soil.

Materials and methods

Twenty earthen pots were used for 4 treatments (5 pots per each treatment). Five pots each for Plain soil (Control), Plain Soil and vermi compost, Plain soil and neem cake, Plain soil and Urea. Ten seed of Rajma was placed in each pot for germination. The germination was counted after 3rd day. . For the measurement of Electrical Conductivity (EC) of root, stem and leaf of 15 days old seedlings were uprooted gently and washed carefully. Two gm. of sample of root, stem and leaf was weighed and homogenized in 20 ml. of distilled water by the help of mortar and pestle separately. The homogenate was centrifuged at 2000 rpm. For 15 minutes. 10 ml of supernatant of each sample was taken out separately and EC was measured. For Protein estimation in root, Stem and leaf, 100mg of root, stem and leaf of the 15 days old seedling grown was homogenized separately in 100ml. of acetate buffer (pH 4.8). The homogenate so obtained was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 15 minutes 2 ml of supernatant was taken out and 10 ml of alkaline copper reagent (prepared by mixing 50 ml of 2% Na₂CO₃ in 0.1 N Noah solution and 1 ml of 0.5% CuSO₄ is 1% sodium potassium tartarate solution) was added. The solution was mixed thoroughly and allowed to stand at room temperature for 10 minutes. One ml of folin ciocalten reagent (1:3 v/v in distilled water) was added rapidly which was followed by vigorous stirring. After 30 minutes, the absorbance of the solution was recorded at 600 nm by systronic calorimeter. The amount of protein in each sample was estimated by comparing the readings with standard curve prepared from albumin.

Results and Discussion

The use of eco friendly farming system is getting more importance , more attention is being paid to the substituting of chemical fertilizers with biological ones (Hu and Barker, 1998). Using the biological fertilizers such as vermicomposts increases the quality and sustainability, in addition to preserving of the environment (Kader et al., 2002). Vermicomposts are produced through interactions between earthworms and micro-organisms in the breakdown of organic wastes (Edwards et al., 2010). Depending on the origin, vermicomposts differ in chemical composition (Handreck, 1986). Vermicomposts are finely divided peat-like materials with high porosity, aeration, drainage, and water-holding capacity. Vermicomposts are usually more stable than their parent materials with increased availability of nutrients and improved physio-chemical and microbiological properties (Edwards and Burrows, 1988; Albanell et al., 1988; Orozco et al., 1996; Atiyeh, 2000). Vermicomposts have the same reported benefits as conventional composts such as a source of organic matter, increased moisture-holding capacity, and enhanced nutrient uptake and plant hormone-like activity (Tomati et al., 1988; Galli et al., 1990; Atiyeh et al., 2002; Bachman and Metzger, 2008). Vermicompost is a sustainable source of macro- and micro-nutrients and have a considerable potential for improving plant growth significantly when used as components of horticultural soils or container media (Sahni et al., 2008).

Table: 1 Germination of Rajma seeds in plain and amended soil

Nature of soil	Mean Germination (% mean +S.E.)				
	Number of days				
	1	2	3	4	5
Plain soil	-	-	50 ±0.02	100 ±0.01	-
Plain soil +Vermicompost	-	-	12 ±0.01	60 ±0.02	90 ±0.04
Plain soil +Neem cake	-	-	-	50 ±0.02	80 ±0.02
Plain soil + Urea	-	-	20 ±0.04	80 ±0.02	100 ±0.01

Table: 2: Electrical conductivity of the extract of root, stem and leaf.

Parts of seedling	Electrical conductivity			
	Plain soil	Plain soil +Vermicompost	Plain soil+ Neem cake	Plain soil+ Urea
Root	0.089±0.004	0.158±0.006	0.095±0.005	0.081±0.004
Stem	0.156±0.006	0.190±0.008	0.159±0.006	0.086±0.004
Leaf	0.138±0.006	0.230±0.012	0.135±0.006	0.158±0.006

Table: 3: Protein contents of the extract of root stem and leaf.

Parts of seedling	Protein content (mg/g)			
	Plain soil	Plain soil +Vermicompost	Plain soil+ Neem cake	Plain soil+ Urea
Root	1.2±0.05	1.0±0.05	0.8±0.03	0.6±0.02
Stem	0.6±0.03	0.6±0.03	0.6±0.03	0.7±0.03
Leaf	0.5±0.01	0.4±0.01	0.5±0.01	0.4±0.01

Vermicompost is formed from pits with lots of pores with high potential of airing, draining, and water retention which prepares an optimum condition in soil (Atiyeh et al., 2001b). Vermicompost in potting media has no detrimental but rather a stimulatory effect on the emergence and root growth of seedlings and has thus, a considerable potential for substituting peat in horticultural potting substrates (Zaller, 2007a, b). Replacing part of the ground soil by different amounts of vermicomposts with different origins leads to increased germination, growth and flowering in laboratory and greenhouse condition in a vast variety of ornamental plants and vegetables such as marigold (Atiyeh et al., 2001a), tomato (Atiyeh et al., 2001b) and pepper (Arancon et al., 2004). Liliaceae belongs to the Liliaceae family. Lilies are of special economic importance because they possess big, beautiful and attractive flowers. This plant is known as one of the important bulbous products and has possessed the 7th position among the cut flowers of the world (Varshney et al., 2000). Despite the proposed enhancing effects of vermicompost, it is stated that high level of it could have inhibiting effect on the plant growth and development, this could be probably due to plant stress by its high soluble salt concentration (Wang et al., 2010). The results of some studies indicated that the application of some levels of vermicompost did not result in significantly increased plant growth and linear relationship between applied vermicompost levels and growth and development of treated plants have not been observed. Atiyeh et al. (2000) reported that lower concentrations of vermicomposts (<50%) into potting mixtures produced greater tomato plant growth and yield effects than the higher concentrations.

High rates of vermicompost substitution may cause adverse effects on plant growth and yield (Arancon et al., 2004). Greater proportions of vermicomposts substituted in growth media have not improved plant growth as much as smaller proportions (Atiyeh et al., 1999, 2000, 2001, 2002). Crop

plants are sensitive to the negative effects of vermicompost at early stages of development (Ievinsh, 2011). Vermicompost substitution inhibited seed germination and seedling growth with almost linear decrease of growth with an increasing concentration of vermicopost in the substrate (Ievinsh, 2011). It is suggested that, vermicompost must be applied cautiously for practical purposes of plant propagation (Ievinsh, 2011). Therefore, the determination of considerable growth inducing levels of vermicompost for reducing costs of agriculture is essential.

In plain soil germination rate of Rajma seeds was 50% on the 3rd day and 100% on the 4th day after sowing the seeds. In the vermicompost amended soil germination rate was 10% on the 3rd day, 50% germination on the 4th day while 90% germination was observed on the 5th day after sowing the seeds. In the neem cake amended soil germination rate was 50% on the 4th day, 80% germination on the 5th day. Soil amended with urea germination was 20% on the 3rd day, 80% on the 4th day and 100% on the 5th day after sowing the seeds. The % germination of seeds in the plain soil was 100% on the 4th day while it was only 60% both in vermicompost and neem cake amended soil on the 4th day after sowing the seeds. However the account of percent germination was enhanced on the 5th day in both the cases.

These experiment together with others retired earlier showed that vermicompost have considerable potential to improve plant growth when used as components of horticulture soil. However the experimental result showed that the germination was declined by 10% in the soil added with vermicompost in comparison of plain soil. It is possible that the high pH of these materials have raised the pH of horticulture soil to a degree proportional to the amount of vermicompost (Gallardo Lava and Hogales, 1987), resulting in a reduced germination as compared to the plain soil.

The EC of root extract obtained from the seedlings grown in the amended with urea was less. The EC of the root extract of the seedlings grown in vermicompost amended soil was more than that of EC of the root extract of seedlings grown in plain soil and neem cake amended soil. The EC of stem extract showed more or less similar pattern of result to that of EC of the root extract. The leaf extract showed less EC in the soil amended with neem cake. The EC of the leaf extract obtained from the seedlings grown in the vermicompost amended soil showed more that of the leaf extract obtained from the seedlings grown in plain soil and in the urea amended soil.

The protein contents of root extract of 25 days old seedlings grown in plain soil showed more amount while it was less in case of root extract of seedlings grown in urea amended soil. The protein contents of the root extract obtained from the seedlings grown in the vermicompost amended soil and soil amended with neem cake was slightly lower than that of plain soil. The protein contents of the stem extract obtained from the seedlings grown in plain soil and in the soil amended with vermicompost and neem cake was same. The protein contents of the stem extract obtained from the seedlings grown in the soil amended with urea was slightly more in comparison to the protein contents of stem extract obtained from the seedlings grown in plain soil and soil amended with vermicompost and neem cake. The protein contents in the leaf extract of the seedlings grown in plain soil and in the soil amended with urea was same and was slightly more that the protein contents of the leaf extract of the seedlings grown in the vermicompost and urea amended soil. The protein contents of the leaf extract of the seedling grown in the soil amended with vermicompost and urea was also same. In order all results the amount of protein contents in the roots of plain and amended soil was much higher than the stem and leaf.

After studying morphological behavior and biological analysis of 45 days mature plants of *P. vulgaris* (Rajma) grown in plain soil and amended soil, it has been found out that the mature plants grown

in the soil amended with neem cake showed enhanced root length and shoot length in comparison to the root and shoot length of matured plants grown in plain soil and in the soil amended with vermicompost and urea.

So far, the number of leaves is considered 45 days matured plants showed maximum number of leaves in the plants grown in vermicompost amended soil, neem cake amended soil and soil amended with urea while plants grown in plain soil showed minimum number of leaves. The number of leaves in amended soil was similar in each case. On the basis of experimental results it was found that urea amended soil reduces root and shoot length in natural plants of 45 days. Similar trend was observed in case of number of node and internodes of mature plants. Maximum number of node and internodes was observed in matured plants grown in neem cake amended soil while urea amended soil affected adversely.

The leaf area of the matured plants when observed it was found that maximum leaf area observed in the matured plants grown in the soil amended with vermicompost. The minimum leaf area was observed in the matured plants grown in the soil amended with urea. Plain soil amended with neem cake also enhanced growth of leaf area in matured plants but less than the matured plants grown in the soil amended with vermicompost. Thus vermicompost favours increase in soil enzyme activities such as – urease, phosphomonoesterase, phosphodiesterase and aryl sulphatase (Albiach et al; 2000). The soil quality includes soil reaction (pH), mineral nutrients, water contents, soil atmosphere and biotic factors. Manure compost when added to soil directly affected almost all of these factors (Marinari et al; 2000). Atiyeh et al; (2001b) reported that the increase of vermicompost rate in the soil resulted in the decrease in soil pH. The production of NH₄; CO₂ and organic acids during microbial metabolism in vermicompost may be contributed to decrease in soil pH (Albanell et al; 1988). There was no report on the effect of plant morphogenesis as well as chemical constituents in the plant body when the “Rajma” seeds grown in the soil amended with neem cake and urea. Only fragmentary reports are available for the rate of vermicompost on the morphogenesis of plants. Hence this study has been carried out.

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